

Vitamin C for Photo-Stable Non-Fullerene-Acceptor Based Organic Solar Cells

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ABSTRACT: The recent advent of the new class of organic molecules, the so-called non-fullerene acceptors, have resulted in skyrocketing power conversion efficiencies of organic solar cells. However, rapid degradation occurs under illumination, particularly when photocatalytic metal oxide electron transport layers are used in these devices. We introduced vitamin C (ascorbic acid) into the organic solar cells as a photostabilizer, and systematically studied its photostabilizing effect on inverted PBDB-T:IT-4F devices. The presence of vitamin C as an antioxidant layer between the ZnO electron transport layer and the photoactive layer strongly suppressed the photocatalytic effect of ZnO that induces NFA photodegradation. Upon 96 h of exposure to AM 1.5G 1 Sun irradiation, the reference devices lost 64 % of their initial efficiency, while those containing vitamin C lost only 38 %. The UV-visible absorption, impedance spectroscopy, and light-dependent voltage and current measurements reveal that vitamin C reduces the photobleaching of NFA molecules and suppresses the charge recombination. This simple approach using a low-cost, naturally occurring antioxidant, provides an efficient strategy for improving photostability of organic semiconductor-based devices.

1.Introduction

Organic solar cells (OSC) have emerged as a promising photovoltaic technology, having the advantage of solution processability that makes them compatible with cost-effective roll-to-roll printing processes that can be applied on thin flexible substrates.¹⁻³ It offers a wide variety of applications such as building-integrated photovoltaics, agrivoltaics, Internet of Things (IOT), wearable electronics and semi-transparent windows.⁴⁻⁹ To date, OSC have reached a power conversion efficiency (*PCE*) of over 19 %, boosted by the development of novel non-fullerene acceptors (NFA).¹⁰⁻¹⁴ However, the stability of these devices still requires further improvements.

A lot of effort has been made to understand the degradation mechanisms, to improve the device stability and lifetime.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ So far, various degradation mechanisms have been identified, and the main stress factors include UV-vis irradiation, heat, oxygen and humidity. Penetration of humidity and oxygen leads to a serious degradation of the active layer, interface layers and the electrodes, and the degradation factor can be accelerated in the presence of UV-vis irradiation. This type of degradation can be avoided or slowed down by proper encapsulation.²⁰⁻²³ The other major issue that affects the devices' lifetime is poor photostability under constant UV-vis irradiation, even in nitrogen-controlled conditions.²⁴⁻²⁸ It has been reported that some NFA OSC show excellent photostability under white LED light (without UV part), with an extrapolated T80 lifetime well beyond 10 years.²⁹ However, it is still challenging to achieve good photostability for NFA OSC under air mass (AM) 1.5 illumination spectrum (100 mW cm^{-2}), which contains a small amount of UV light (2 mW cm^{-2}).³⁰⁻³¹

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is commonly used as an electron transport layer (ETL) in inverted NFA OSC, because of its high optical transparency as well as well-matched work function and conduction band minimum, providing n-type character with charge carrier selectivity due to a low-lying valence band. In addition, its low cost, easy synthesis and simple solution processability makes it industrially viable.^{32,33} Despite these advantages ZnO ETL is photocatalytically active, which leads to decomposition and photooxidation of organic molecules (e.g. NFA) on the surface of ZnO, via redox reactions and formation of hydroxyl radicals.³¹ This subsequently leads to charge accumulation and recombination at the ZnO interface, which both strongly reduce the device stability.^{29,34,35} Various approaches have been explored to control such interfacial degradation: Su and co-workers³⁶ utilized nitrogen and sulfur-doped graphene oxide nanosheets (NS-GNS) as a modifier layer for ZnO, Hu et al.³⁷ used aqueous polyethylenimine as a modifier layer, Liu et al.

³⁸ developed modified ZnO layers, Me-ZnO, DMSO-ZnO, and sol-gel-ZnO, Xu et.al used C60 self-assembled monolayer (SAM) as a protective buffer layer.³⁹ Recently, U. K. Aryal et al. demonstrated that 2D Mxene could be embedded with ZnO to reduce this photocatalytic decomposition on ZnO surface.⁴⁰ In this work, we investigate the stabilization effect using a naturally occurring antioxidant interlayer between ZnO and active layer.

We have previously demonstrated a successful new pathway of stabilizing organic solar cells by introducing antioxidants as the third component in the active layer, which interferes with the photooxidation process by deactivating the reactive oxygen species (ROS), by scavenging radicals, or by acting as a barrier to UV irradiation.⁴¹⁻⁴³ Recently, we have reported an improved photostability for OSC devices using naturally occurring antioxidant molecule, β -carotene, as an effective quencher of singlet oxygen and its precursors.⁴⁴ We also demonstrated a rapidly improved devices' lifetime using a multifunctional additive, consisting of another carotenoid antioxidant, astaxanthin, covalently bonded to a polymeric organosilicon, which at the same time increases the photooxidative stability of the devices and improves their mechanical integrity.⁴⁵ This antioxidant-assisted stabilization approach has been as well reported effective in NFA-based active layers.^{46,47}

In this work, we use a naturally occurring antioxidant molecule, vitamin C (ascorbic acid), as an ultrathin interlayer that suppresses the ZnO-influenced photocatalytic degradation of NFA-based active layers, resulting in extended stability of the devices. We found that vitamin C as an interlayer significantly suppresses the photocatalytically activated bleaching of IT-4F, as evident from UV-vis absorption spectroscopy. Impedance spectroscopy (IS) analysis revealed higher recombination resistance values (R_{rec}) for vitamin C based devices, which can be attributed to lower recombination losses as compared to the reference devices. Consequently, vitamin C based devices

showed better photostability, maintaining 64 % of their original value even after 96 h illumination under air mass (AM) 1.5 illumination spectrum (100 mW cm⁻²), as compared to reference devices which retain only 38 %.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Device Properties

Vitamin C is a potent reducing agent that has a very low redox potential, which enables it to react with almost all oxidizing free radicals, among them also the hydroxyl radicals and superoxide radical anions,^{48,49} which are known to be photooxidative intermediates in the degradation process of several types of NFA molecules.⁵⁰ It is found at high concentrations in many animal tissues and plants, and it is also extensively used as an antioxidant in a great variety of products and food industry.⁵¹ In this work, we systematically analyze the stabilizing effect of vitamin C on PBDB-T:IT-4F (Poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl) thiophen-2-yl)-benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(5,5-(1',3'-di-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl)benzo[1',2'-c:4',5'-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione)) : 3,9-bis(2-methylene-((3-(1,1-dicyanomethylene)-6,7-difluoro)-indanone))-5,5,11,11-tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-dithieno[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']dithiophene) organic solar cells. To understand the impact of vitamin C on device performance and stability, the ZnO layer was treated with vitamin C as a passivation layer for the inverted OSC devices. Optical absorption measurements were carried out, demonstrating that the addition of the vitamin C layer does not modify the optical properties of the ZnO based ETL (**Figure S1**). The thickness of the vitamin C layer was optimized by dissolving various concentrations of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) in ethanol solution, which were spin-coated at different RPM on the ZnO films. It is observed that a higher thickness of vitamin C interlayer has a negative effect on device efficiency, and devices suffer

from an S-shape characteristics (**Figure S2**).⁵² With optimization of vitamin C concentration at 1 mg/ml in ethanol, coated at 3000 RPM (~ 2 nm), the best device efficiency of 9.97 % with J_{sc} of 21.57 mA/cm², FF of 66 % and V_{oc} of 0.69 V was obtained, which is marginally higher compared to the pristine ZnO devices, which exhibit 9.85 %, 21.02 mA/cm², 68 % and 0.68 V. The device architecture employed was indium tin oxide (ITO)/ZnO/vitamin C/PBDB-T:IT-4F/MoO_x/Ag (**Figure 1a**). The chemical structures of the donor and acceptor molecules are also shown in **Figure 1a**. Their corresponding light current density-voltage $J(V)$ curves and EQE, measured under AM 1.5G light intensity (100 mW/cm²), are shown in **Figure 1b** and **1c**, and their corresponding solar cell parameters are summarized in **Table 1**. EQE spectra shows that both the control and vitamin C devices show strong photo response from 500 to 800 nm with similar spectral shapes, and the trend is well correlated with the $J(V)$ curves. **Figure 1d** represent the PCE histogram plot for 12 individual ZnO and ZnO/vitamin C based devices.

Figure 1. (a) Inverted device layer stack and molecular structures of vitamin C, PBDB-T and IT-4F, (b, c) Light $J(V)$ and EQE characteristics of PBDBT:IT-4F devices, (d) Histogram of PBDBT:IT-4F device with ZnO and the ZnO modified with vitamin C.

Table 1. Solar cell parameters of PBDBT:IT-4F devices with and without vitamin C as the interfacial layer between ZnO and active layer. The values in the parentheses are the average values obtained for 12 devices

Interface layer	V_{oc} [V]	J_{sc} [mA/cm ²]	FF [%]	PCE [%]
ZnO	0.68	21.02	67.82	9.85
	(0.66±0.02)	(20.19±0.42)	(67.66±0.54)	(9.16±0.42)
ZnO/vitamin C	0.69	21.57	65.84	9.97
	(0.68±0.002)	(21.38±0.24)	(65.27±0.54)	(9.75±0.0.13)

2.2 Photostability improvement of OSC in the presence of vitamin C

The photostability of encapsulated devices was tested in a lifetime setup with automated measurements at every 30 minutes under open circuit conditions. The measurements were conducted on cells containing slightly thicker vitamin C interlayer (2 mg/ml, 4000 RPM), as they provide more repeatability with smaller error bars (see **Figure S3**), making it easier to conclude on the stability. However, we know that the stability trend for the thinner vitamin C interlayers follows the same trend (see **Figure S4**). **Figure 2** and **Table 2.** compare the evolution of PCE , FF , J_{sc} and V_{oc} of encapsulated devices without and with the vitamin C interlayer, under continuous exposure to 1 Sun AM1.5G irradiation. The PCE evolution of reference devices, containing pure ZnO ETL, suffers from a strong burn-in of 44 % in magnitude, as compared to the vitamin C devices that lose only 23 %. Also, the burn-in dynamics are slowed down in presence of vitamin

C - its duration is 29.9 h, as compared to the reference burn-in period of 22.7 h. The same improvement is seen in T80 - the reference devices reach it after 64.2 h, and vitamin C devices after 81.5 h. It is to note that over the duration of this experiment of 96 hours, the vitamin C devices retained 64 % of their original *PCE*, while the reference devices retained only 38 %. Thus, the presence of vitamin C resulted in an overall 50 % increase of the accumulated power generation (APG) over the lifetime of the devices. The *PCE* decay of reference devices originates mainly from a reduction in *FF* ($\approx 40\%$), with the additional contribution of J_{sc} ($\approx 20\%$) and V_{oc} ($\approx 15\%$). Such a trend in *FF* was observed in similar active layer systems containing 1,8-diiodooctane, and demonstrated to arise due to the 1,8-diiodooctane evaporation, which results in the disconnection of neighboring polymer domains in the active layer that then act as traps for free charge carriers.⁵³ All of the vitamin C-treated devices, regardless of the thickness (i.e., spin speeds of 1000, 2000, 3000 and 4000 rpm) resulted in a higher photostability as compared to the reference devices that contain pure ZnO ETL, as shown in **Figure S4**.

Figure 2. Evolution of solar cell parameters (PCE , V_{oc} , J_{sc} , and FF) of encapsulated PBDB-T:IT-4F devices without and with vitamin C interlayer, under continuous 1 Sun AM 1.5G irradiation in ambient atmosphere at 35°C. Data points represent the average over eight devices, normalized with respect to the initial data point, with the standard deviations as the error bar.

Table 2. Summary of degradation parameters of PBDBT:IT-4F devices, reference and with vitamin C interlayer, under AM 1.5G irradiation at 100 mW cm⁻² in N₂. For extracted parameters of the bi-exponential fit and the fitting errors, see **Table S2**.

	$t_{burn-in}$ [h]	$PCE_{burn-in}$ [%]	PCE_{80} [%]	t_{80} [h]	$t_{lifetime}$ [h]	$PCE_{initial}$ [%]	$PCE_{burn-in}/PCE_{initial}$ [%]	$APG_{lifetime}$ [kWhm ⁻²]
Ref	22.7	3.1	2.5	64.2	41.5	5.6	55.6	1.4
vitamin C	29.9	3.9	3.1	81.5	51.6	5.1	76.6	2.1

Figure 3a and **3c** show the light $J(V)$ characteristics of reference and devices with vitamin C at different stages of photodegradation. We can observe a strong trend in reference devices, leading up to a 5-fold increase in series resistance and a decrease in the shunt resistance over the time of exposure. Under the same conditions, the devices containing the vitamin C interlayer are much less affected, as also shown in **Table S3**. To further understand the degradation nature, dark $J(V)$ characteristics were measured and their semilogarithmic plots are shown in **Figure 3b** and **3d**. The dark $J(V)$ curves of the reference devices show a significantly higher leakage current in reverse bias over the exposure time, as compared to devices with vitamin C interlayer, exhibiting weaker diode characteristics. In addition, the slope value near the injection region (0.5 V to 1 V) is for the reference devices decreasing over time, indicating the light-induced loss of ETL functionality of ZnO, which is strongly reduced in devices containing vitamin C interlayer.⁵⁴

Figure 3. Light & dark $J(V)$ plots of (a, b) reference ZnO and (c, d) ZnO/vitamin C (4000 rpm) encapsulated devices under continuous exposure to 1 Sun AM 1.5G in ambient atmosphere at 35°C for different durations of up to 96 h.

Figure 4. UV-vis absorption spectra of IT-4F (a-c); PBDBT (d-f); PBDBT:IT-4F (g-i) under continuous exposure to AM 1.5G 1 Sun irradiation in N_2 atmosphere at $35^\circ C$.

2.3 UV-vis stability of pristine and blend films

To further understand the photostabilizing effect of vitamin C on the PBDBT:IT-4F devices, absorption measurements were recorded on films of IT-4F, PBDBT and PBDBT:IT-4F blends, deposited on bare glass, glass coated with ZnO, and glass coated with ZnO and vitamin C, as shown in **Figure 4**. The films were stored in N_2 atmosphere under 1 Sun AM 1.5G irradiation, and

the UV-vis spectra were recorded periodically for up to 80 h of exposure. As shown in **Figure 4 a-c**, IT-4F film undergoes a fast loss of absorption, decaying down to 20 % of initial absorption upon 80 h (**Figure S5 b**). As evident from **Figure 4 g-i**, the same trend can be observed in blend films, and at a less strongly reduced magnitude also in pristine PBDBT films (largest loss on ZnO of only ≈ 5 , as evident from **Figure S5 a**). This can be attributed to the ZnO photocatalytic activity, in which a photoexcited ZnO produces electron-hole pairs that take part in redox reactions to produce hydroxyl radicals and superoxide radical anions, which are strong oxidizing agents⁵⁵ known to readily react and degrade the OPV molecules.⁵⁶⁻⁶⁰ In comparison, IT-4F films in absence of ZnO do not suffer from such strong losses. The same can be achieved in presence of ZnO when a vitamin C interlayer is inserted in between, in which case vitamin C shields the organic molecules from the radical attack originating from ZnO, and thus clearly mitigates this degradation effect.

. To confirm the stability of vitamin C, we performed an absorption study on ZnO and ZnO/vitamin C under light, as shown in Figure S7. The absorption pattern follows same trend and there are no significant changes in the absorption spectrum, indicating that vitamin C does not undergo degradation under our OPV testing conditions.

To further understand the degradation process, Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy was carried out on ZnO/IT-4F and ZnO/vitamin C/IT-4F films under, as shown in Figure S8. The absorption peak arises at 1710 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to stretching vibration of unsaturated carbonyl bond that is resonant with adjacent exocyclic double bond. The aged sample of ZnO/IT-4F shows an additional peak at 1745 cm^{-1} possibly due to the saturated carbonyl bond arising from the breakage of the exocyclic double bond. On the other hand, vitamin C sample shows a stable characteristic peak, indicating that the presence of vitamin C prevents degradation of the IT-4F.³¹

2.4 Recombination analysis using impedance and light intensity dependent measurements

To investigate the effect of the degradation on the electrical characteristics of OSC in presence of vitamin C, Impedance Spectroscopy (IS) measurements were carried out. The measurements were conducted in dark conditions, at 0 V applied potential, with the frequency ranging from 10 Hz to 1 MHz, and 10 mV amplitude.⁶¹⁻⁶⁴ The Nyquist plots of reference devices and devices with vitamin C interlayer, under exposure to, up to 96 hours, of 1 Sun AM 1.5G irradiation, are presented in **Figure 5 a, b**. The results were fitted using an equivalent-circuit model (ECM) shown in **Figure S9**. The decrease in the semi-circle radii as the devices are degraded is explained by the decrease in the charge recombination resistance (R_{rec}) according to the model employed.³⁶ **Table 3** tracks the progression of the fitted non-radiative recombination resistance values for reference devices and devices containing vitamin C interlayer upon exposure to 1 Sun AM 1.5G irradiation for up to 96 hours. From the table (also refer to **Figure S10**) it is clear that reference devices undergo a significant reduction in R_{rec} value ($\approx 80\%$ loss at 96 h), while the devices containing vitamin C interlayer lose only 50% at the same time. This clearly shows that the reference devices, in which the ZnO ETL is in direct contact with the PBDB-T:IT-4F active layer, suffer from severe charge recombination increase upon exposure to light. In addition, the initial R_{rec} value for devices containing a vitamin C interlayer is two orders of magnitude higher than that of the reference devices, indicating that vitamin C suppresses the recombination. The suppression of defects with vitamin C was further verified using the capacitance measurements.

To quantify the change in the built-in electric field (V_{BI}) for fresh and photodegraded devices, capacitance-voltage measurements were carried out on reference devices and devices containing vitamin C interlayer. The related $C^{-2}(V)$ curves of the fresh and aged devices are shown in **Figure 5 c, d**. The built-in potential (V_{BI}) was calculated by the Mott-Schottky equation:⁶¹⁻⁶⁴

$$C_{sc}^{-2} = 2(V_{BI}-V)/(A^2q\epsilon_r\epsilon_0N_A)$$

where C_{sc} is the value of the capacitance of the space-charge region, V the applied voltage, q the elementary charge, A the device area, ϵ_r and ϵ_0 the relative dielectric constant estimated by the geometric capacitance measured at 10 kHz at 0 V and the vacuum permittivity (see **Table S4**). For organic semiconductors, the above equation can be applied assuming that the defect states are the only contributors to the charge carriers in the depletion layer of the p-n junction. Thus, N_A corresponds to the density of defects.^{62,64} For more information on the calculation of the relative dielectric constant, please see SI. The respective values are tabulated in **Table 3**. As shown in **Figure 5 e, f**, the V_{BI} value of reference devices drops over time under light stress from 0.572 to 0.549 V ($\approx 5\%$ loss). Meanwhile, under the same conditions, in the devices with vitamin C interlayer, the decrease in V_{BI} is lower ($\leq 1.0\%$, from 0.568 to 0.565 V). This relation is in good agreement with the observed V_{oc} drop in the lifetime measurements (see **Figure 2**). N_A value raises in both reference and vitamin C devices and reaches similar values, however, the rise of N_A in the initial period (after 24 h) is much steeper for reference devices (from 1.43×10^{20} to $2.90 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), as compared to vitamin C devices (from 1.33×10^{20} to $1.86 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The latter indicates that the reference devices degrade faster. This is in accordance with the strong burn-in observed for reference devices. Moreover, the capacitance-frequency $C(f)$ plots show a gradual increase in the capacitance at frequencies below 100 Hz (**Figure S8**). According to Xu et al., this behavior is attributed to the presence of deep defect states.⁶⁵ Conversely, the vitamin C interlayer devices show a flat response, indicating a low presence of deep defect states.

Light-intensity dependent measurements were performed to further understand the impact of vitamin C interlayer on the charge recombination. First, we examined the J_{sc} variation under different light intensities. In general, J_{sc} directly depends on the light intensity, as described by the

following relationship: $J_{sc} \propto P_{in}^\alpha$; where α equal to unity is the signature of no bimolecular recombination. As shown in **Figure S9**, both reference and devices with vitamin C interlayer show a linear dependence of J_{sc} to light intensity, implying weak bimolecular recombination.⁶⁶ Subsequently, we examined the relationship between V_{oc} and light intensity, as shown in **Figure 6**. Generally, V_{oc} is directly related to $\ln(P_{in}) n k_B T/q$, where P_{in} is the light intensity, n the ideality factor, k_B the Boltzmann constant, T the absolute temperature, and q the elementary charge. If the slope value is close to $k_B T/q$, the bimolecular recombination is dominating, while for the slope values near $2 k_B T/q$, the trap-assisted recombination is dominating.⁶⁶ As shown in **Figure 6a**, the slope value of reference devices increases over 96 h of light exposure from $1.41 k_B T/q$ to $2.18 k_B T/q$, while that of devices containing vitamin C interlayer decreases less (from $1.44 k_B T/q$ to $1.84 k_B T/q$). This indicates a suppression of trap-assisted charge recombination in devices containing vitamin C interlayer, as compared to the reference devices. This is consistent with the degradation of ITIC molecules at the ZnO interfaces due to photocatalytic reactions, leading to increased charge carrier accumulation and recombination close to that interface.

Figure 5. (a, b) Nyquist plots; (c, d) Capacitance as a function of applied voltage at 10 kHz; (e, f) built-in voltage (V_{BI}) and density of defects (N_A), of reference PBDBT:IT-4F devices containing a pure ZnO as ETL and devices containing a vitamin C interlayer between the active layer and ZnO (ZnO/vitamin C), under exposure to 1 Sun AM 1.5G irradiation.

Table 3: Parameters of fitted data using the equivalent circuit and capacitance measurements.

Reference devices (with pure ZnO)				Devices with vitamin C (4000 rpm) interlayer		
t (h)	R_{rec} (k Ω)	V_{BI} (V)	N_A (cm $^{-3}$)	R_{rec} (k Ω)	V_{BI} (V)	N_A (cm $^{-3}$)
0	6570	0.572	1.43×10^{20}	2.22×10^5	0.568	1.33×10^{20}
24	849	0.549	2.86×10^{20}	1.28×10^5	0.564	1.86×10^{20}
48	571	0.542	3.25×10^{20}	7.61×10^4	0.550	2.23×10^{20}
96	605	0.540	3.40×10^{20}	4.80×10^4	0.549	3.44×10^{20}

Figure 6. Light-intensity dependent V_{oc} (expressed as the percentage of 1 Sun irradiation) for (a) reference, and (b) devices with vitamin C interlayer, under exposure to 1 Sun AM 1.5G irradiation for increasing time intervals.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we have demonstrated that vitamin C employed as an interlayer between ZnO ETL and the active layer can greatly improve the photostability of NFA OSC. After 96 h of continuous

photodegradation under 1 Sun, devices containing vitamin C interlayer retain 62 % of their original value, while reference devices retain only 36 %. The major reason for this stabilization can be found in the capability of vitamin C to act as an antioxidant, which scavenges the radicals formed in the photocatalytic decomposition of the active layer molecules facilitated by ZnO electron transport layer. The application of naturally occurring antioxidants for interface materials, as demonstrated in this work, brings us one step closer towards the realization of fully green, bio-based and stable high-efficiency organic solar cells for commercial applications.

Experimental Section

Materials: L-ascorbic acid (≥ 99 % purity), chlorobenzene, zinc oxide ink and 1,8-diiodooctane were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Polymer donor (PBDB-T) and non-fullerene acceptor (IT-4F) were purchased from 1-Materials (Canada). All reagents were used as such without further purification.

Device fabrication and Characterization: The patterned ITO-coated glass substrates were sonicated in a soap solution, deionized water, acetone and isopropyl alcohol, each for 15 minutes. The cleaned substrates were UV-ozone treated for 30 minutes. After that, ZnO nanoparticles were spin-coated at 3000 rpm for 60 seconds and annealed at 130 °C for 15 minutes. To create the vitamin C interlayer, 1 mg of vitamin C was dissolved in 1 ml of ethanol, and spin-coated with various spin speeds for 60 seconds, and subsequently annealed at 110 °C for 5 minutes. Photoactive layers were deposited from PBDBT:IT-4F solution in chlorobenzene (and 0.5 % of 1,8-diiodooctane), in the weight ratio of 1:1. The blend solution was spin-coated at 2500 rpm for 60 seconds (corresponding to the thickness of ≈ 100 nm), and subsequently annealed at 110 °C for 10 minutes. A 10 nm film of MoOx was thermally evaporated as the hole transport layer, followed by a silver

contact layer with a thickness of 100 nm (deposition rate 0.05 \AA s^{-1} , deposition pressure $\approx 5 \times 10^{-7}$ Torr). The current density–voltage $J(V)$ measurements were recorded using ABET technology solar simulator (class AAA) under 1 Sun condition with the intensity of 100 mW cm^{-2} . EQE measurements were carried out using Bentham TMc 300 Monochromator. Stability tests were performed using a home-built controllable automatic measurement setup and an infinityPV ISO Sun solar simulator lamp, under open circuit conditions. UV-vis absorption spectra of the thin films were recorded using a UV-2700 Shimadzu, in the wavelength range 330–830 nm. Impedance spectra were measured in dark using Biologic SP-150e.

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ABBREVIATIONS

OSC, Organic solar cells ; PCE, Power Conversion Efficiency ; NFA, Non-Fullerene Acceptors, ROS, Reactive Oxygen Species.

References

(1) Ng, L. W. T.; Lee, S. W.; Chang, D. W.; Hodgkiss, J. M.; Vak, D. Organic Photovoltaics' New Renaissance: Advances Toward Roll-to-Roll Manufacturing of Non-Fullerene Acceptor Organic Photovoltaics. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2022**, *7*, 2101556–2101586.

(2) van der Staaij, F. M.; van Keulen, I. M.; von Hauff, E. Organic Photovoltaics: Where Are We Headed? *Sol. RRL.* **2021**, *5*, 2100167–2100174.

(3) Meddeb, H.; Götz-Köhler, M.; Neugebohrn, N.; Banik, U.; Osterthun, N.; Sergeev, O.; Berends, D.; Lattyak, C.; Gehrke, K.; Vehse, M. Tunable Photovoltaics: Adapting Solar Cell Technologies to Versatile Applications. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, *12*, 2200713–2200772.

(4) Cui, Y.; Hong, L.; Hou, J. Organic Photovoltaic Cells for Indoor Applications: Opportunities and Challenges, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* **2020**, *12*, 38815–38828.

(5) Kim, Y.J.; Park, S.E.; Cho, B. J. A Wearable Organic Photovoltaic-Thermoelectric (OPV-TE) Hybrid Generator to Minimize the Open-Circuit Voltage Losses of OPV Module, *Nano Energy.* **2022**, *93*, 106775–106785.

(6) Jahandar, M.; Kim, S.; Lim, D. C. Indoor Organic Photovoltaics for Self-Sustaining IoT Devices: Progress, Challenges and Practicalization, *ChemSusChem.* **2021**, *14*, 3449–3474

- (7) Li, Z.; Ma, T.; Yang, H.; Lu, L.; Wang, R. Transparent and Colored Solar Photovoltaics for Building Integration. *Sol. RRL.* **2021**, *5*, 2000614–2000623.
- (8) Hatamvand, M.; Kamrani, E.; Lira-Cantu, M.; Madsen, M.; Patil, B. R.; Vivo, P.; Mehmood, M. S.; Numan, A.; Ahmed, I.; Zhan, Y. Recent Advances in Fiber-Shaped and Planar-Shaped Textile Solar Cells. *Nano Energy* **2020**, *71*, 104609–104625.
- (9) Ravishankar, E.; Charles, M.; Xiong, Y.; Henry, R.; Swift, J.; Rech, J.; Calero, J.; Cho, S.; Booth, R.E.; Kim, T.; Balzer, A.H.; Qin, Y.; Ho, C.H.Y.; So, F.; Stingelin, N.; Amassian, A.; Saravitz, C.; You, W.; Ade, H.; Sederoff, H.; Connor, B. T. O. Balancing Crop Production and Energy Harvesting in Organic Solar-Powered Greenhouses, *Cell Reports Physical Science* **2021**, *3*, 100381–100400.
- (10) Zhu, L., Zhang, M., Xu, J. et al. Single-Junction Organic Solar Cells with Over 19% Efficiency Enabled by a Refined Double-Fibril Network Morphology. *Nat. Mater.* **2022**, *21*, 656–663.
- (11) Gao, W.; Qi, F.; Peng, Z.; Francis R. Lin, Kui Jiang, Zhong, C.; Kaminsky, W.; Guan, Z.; Chun-Sing Lee, Marks, T. J; Ade, H.; Jen A. K-Y. Achieving 19% Power Conversion Efficiency in Planar-Mixed Heterojunction Organic Solar Cells Using a Pseudosymmetric Electron Acceptor. *Adv. Mater.* **2022**, *34*, 2202089–2202100.
- (12) Wang, J.; Zheng, Z.; Zu, Y.; Wang, Y.; Liu, X.; Zhang, S.; Zhang, M.; Hou, J. A. Tandem Organic Photovoltaic Cell with 19.6% Efficiency Enabled by Light Distribution Control. *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, *33*, 2102787–2102795.

- (13) Cui, Y.; Xu, Y.; Yao, H.; Bi, P.; Hong, L.; Zhang, J.; Zu, Y.; Zhang, T.; Qin, J.; Ren, J.; Chen, Z.; He, C.; Hao, X.; Wei, Z.; Hou, J. Single-Junction Organic Photovoltaic Cell with 19% Efficiency. *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, *33*, 2102420–2102427.
- (14) Zhang, G.; Zhao, J.; Chow, P. C. Y.; Zhang, J.; Zhu, Z.; Zhang, J.; Huang, F.; Yan, H. Nonfullerene Acceptor Molecules for Bulk Heterojunction Solar Cells. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 3447–3507.
- (15) Cheng, P.; Zhan, X. Stability of Organic Solar Cells: Challenges and Strategies, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2016**, *45*, 2544–2582.
- (16) Rafique, S.; Abdullah, S.M.; Sulaiman, K.; Iwamoto, M. Fundamentals of Bulk Heterojunction Organic Solar Cells: An Overview of Stability/Degradation Issues and Strategies for Improvement, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **2018**, *84*, 43–53.
- (17) Jørgensen, M.; Norrman, K.; Gevorgyan, S.A.; Tromholt, T.; Andreasen, B.; Krebs, F.C. Stability of Polymer Solar Cells, *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 580–612.
- (18) Greenbank, W.; Djeddaoui, N.; Destouesse, E.; Lamminaho, J.; Prete, M.; Boukezzi, L.; Ebel, T.; Bessissa, L.; Rubahn, H-G.; Turkovic, V.; Madsen, M. Degradation Behavior of Scalable Nonfullerene Organic Solar Cells Assessed by Outdoor and Indoor ISOS Stability Protocols, *Energy Technol.* **2020**, *8*, 2000295–2000304.
- (19) Arredondo, B.; Carlos Pérez-Martínez, J.; Muñoz-Díaz, L.; López-González, M. D. C.; Martín-Martín, D.; del Pozo, G.; Hernández-Balaguera, E.; Romero, B.; Lamminaho, J.; Turkovic, V.; Madsen, M. Influence of Solvent Additive on the Performance and Aging Behavior of Non-Fullerene Organic Solar Cells, *Solar Energy* **2022**, *232*, 120–127.

- (20) Cros, S.; de Bettignies, R.; Berson, S.; Bailly, S.; Maise, P.; Lemaitre, N.; Guillerea, S. Definition of Encapsulation Barrier Requirements: A Method Applied to Organic Solar Cells, *Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells*. **2011**, 95, S65–S69.
- (21) Sutherland, L.J.; Weerasinghe, H.C.; Simon, G. P. A Review on Emerging Barrier Materials and Encapsulation Strategies for Flexible Perovskite and Organic Photovoltaics, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2021**, 11, 2101383–2101414.
- (22) Arredondo, B.; Pozo, G.D.; Hernández-Balaguera, E.; Martín, D.M.; Carmen López González, Romero, B.; López-Fraguas, E.; Vergaz, R.; Quintana, X.; Lamminaho, J.; Destouesse, E.; Ahmadpour, M.; Turkovic, V.; Madsen, M. Identification of Degradation Mechanisms in Slot-Die-Coated Nonfullerene ITO-Free Organic Solar Cells Using Different Illumination Spectra, *ACS Applied Energy Materials*. **2020**, 3, 6476–6485.
- (23) Destouesse, E.; Top, M.; Lamminaho, J.; Rubahn, H.-G.; Fahlteich, J.; Madsen, M. Slot-Die Processing and Encapsulation of Non-Fullerene Based ITO-Free Organic Solar Cells and Modules. *Flexible Printed Electron*. **2019**, 4, 045004–045012.
- (24) Mateker, W.R.; McGehee, M. D. Progress in Understanding Degradation Mechanisms and Improving Stability in Organic Photovoltaics, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, 28, 1603940–603955.
- (25) Mateker, W.R.; Sachs-Quintana, I.T.; Burkhard, G.F.; Cheacharoen, R.; McGehee, M. D. Minimal Long-Term Intrinsic Degradation Observed in a Polymer solar Cell Illuminated in an Oxygen-Free Environment, *Chem. Mater.* **2015**, 27, 404–407.
- (26) Che, y.; Niazi, M.R.; Izquierdo, R.; Perepichka, D. F. Mechanism of the Photodegradation of A-D-A Acceptors for Organic Photovoltaics, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, 60, 24833–24837.

- (27) Turkovic, V.; Engmann, S.; Egbe, D. A.M.; Himmerlich, M.; Krischok, S.; Gobsch, G.; Hoppe, H. Multiple Stress Degradation Analysis of the Active Layer in Organic Photovoltaics, *Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells*. **2014**, 120, 654–668.
- (28) Ciammaruchi, L.; Oliveira, R.; Charas, A.; Tulus, N. N.; von Hauff, E.; Polino, G.; Brunetti, F.; Hansson, R.; Moons, E.; Krassas, M.; Kakavelakis, G.; Kymakis, E.; Sánchez, J. G.; Ferreburrull, J.; Marsal, L. F.; Züfle, S.; Fluhr, D.; Roesch, R.; Faber, T.; et al. Stability of Organic Solar Cells with PCDTBT Donor Polymer : an Interlaboratory Study. *Journal of Materials Research* **2018**, 33, 1909–1924.
- (29) Du, X.; Heumueller, T.; Gruber, W.; Classen, A.; Unruh, T.; Li, N.; Brabec, C. J. Efficient Polymer Solar Cells Based on Non-fullerene Acceptors with Potential Device Lifetime Approaching 10 Years, *Joule*. **2019**, 3, 215–226.
- (30) Jiang, Y.; Sun, L.; Jiang, F.; Xie, C.; Hu, L.; Dong, X.; Qin, F.; Liu, T.; Hu, L.; Jiang, X.; Zhou, Y. Photocatalytic Effect of ZnO on the Stability of Nonfullerene Acceptors and its Mitigation by SnO₂ for Nonfullerene Organic Solar Cells, *Mater. Horiz.* **2019**, 6, 1438–1443.
- (31) Park, S.; Son, H. J. Intrinsic Photo-Degradation and Mechanism of Polymer Solar Cells: The Crucial Role of Non-Fullerene Acceptors, *J. Mater. Chem. A*. **2019**, 7, 25830–25837.
- (32) Liu, C.; Xiao, C.; Li, W. Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles as Electron Transporting Interlayer in Organic Solar Cells, *J. Mater. Chem. C*. **2021**, 9, 14093–14114.
- (33) Yin, Z.; Wei, J.; Zheng, Q. Interfacial Materials for Organic Solar Cells: Recent Advances and Perspectives, *Adv.Sci.* **2016**, 3, 1500362–1500398.

- (34) Jiang, P.; Hu, L.; Sun, L.; Li, Z.; Han, H.; Zhou, Y. On the Interface Reactions and Stability of Nonfullerene Organic Solar Cells, *Chem. Sci.* **2022**, 13, 4714–4739.
- (35) Azeez, A.; Narayan, K. S. Dominant Effect of UV-Light-Induced “Burn-in” Degradation in Non-Fullerene Acceptor Based Organic Solar Cells, *J. Phys. Chem. C.* **2021**, 125, 12531–2540.
- (36) Su, L-Y.; Huang, H-H.; Tsai, C-E.; Hou, C-H.; Shyue, J-J.; Lu, C-H.; Pao, C-W.; Yu, M-H.; Wang, L.; Chueh, C-C. Improving Thermal and Photostability of Polymer Solar Cells by Robust Interface Engineering, *Small*, **2022**, 18, 2107834–210745.
- (37) Hu, L.; Jiang, Y.; Sun, L.; Xie, C.; Qin, F.; Wang, W.; Zhou, Y. Significant Enhancement of Illumination Stability of Nonfullerene Organic Solar Cells via an Aqueous Polyethylenimine Modification, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2021**, 12, 2607–2614.
- (38) Liu, B.; Han, Y.; Li, Z.; Gu, H.; Yan, L.; Lin, Y.; Luo, Q.; Yang, S.; Ma, C -Q. Visible Light-Induced Degradation of Inverted Polymer:Non-Fullerene Acceptor Solar Cells: Initiated by the Light Absorption of ZnO Layer, *Sol. RRL.* **2021**, 5, 2000638–2000647.
- (39) Xu, X.; Xiao, J.; Zhang, G.; Wei, L.; Jia, X.; Yip, H -L.; Cao, Y. Interface-Enhanced Organic Solar Cells with Extrapolated T80 Lifetimes of Over 20 years, *Science Bulletin.* **2020**, 65, 208–216.
- (40) Aryal, U.K.; Pazniak, H.; Kumari, T.; Weber, M.; Johansson, F.O.L.; Vannucchi, M.; Witkowski, N.; Turkovic, V.; Carlo, A-D.; Madsen, M. 2D MXene-Based Electron Transport Layers for Nonhalogenated Solvent-Processed Stable Organic Solar Cells, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2023**, 6, 4549–4558.

- (41) Turkovic, V.; Engmann, S.; Tsierkezos, N.; Hoppe, H.; Madsen, M.; Rubahn, H.G.; Ritter, U.; Gobsch, G. Long-Term Stabilization of Organic Solar Cells Using Hydroperoxide Decomposers as Additives, *Appl. Phys. A: Mater. Sci. Process.* **2016**, 112, 255–260.
- (42) Turkovic, V.; Engmann, S.; Tsierkezos, N.; Hoppe, H.; Ritter, U.; Gobsch, G. Long-Term Stabilization of Organic Solar Cells Using Hindered Phenols as Additives, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* **2014**, 6, 18525–18537.
- (43) Turkovic, V.; Engmann, S.; Tsierkezos, N.; Hoppe, H.; Madsen, M.; Rubahn, H.G.; Ritter, U.; Gobsch, G. Long-Term Stabilization of Organic Solar Cells Using UV Absorbers, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **2016**, 49, 125604–125610.
- (44) Turkovic, V.; Prete, M.; Bregnhøj, M.; Inasaridze, L.; Volyniuk, D.; Obrezkov, F. A.; Grazulevicius, J. V.; Engmann, S.; Rubahn, H.-G.; Troshin, P. A.; Ogilby, P. R.; Madsen, M. Biomimetic Approach to Inhibition of Photooxidation in Organic Solar Cells Using BetaCarotene as an Additive. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, 11, 41570–41579.
- (45) Prete, M.; Oglioni, E.; Bregnhøj, M.; Lissau, J.S.; Dastidar, S.; Rubahn, H.-G.; Engmann, S.; Skov, A.L.; Brook, M.A.; Ogilby, P.R.; A. Printz, Turkovic, V.; Madsen, M. Synergistic Effect of Carotenoid and Silicone-Based Additives for Photooxidatively Stable Organic Solar Cells with Enhanced Elasticity, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2021**, 9, 11838–118.
- (46) Guo, J.; Wu, Y.; Sun, R.; Wang, W.; Guo, J.; Wu, Q.; Tang, X.; Sun, C.; Luo, Z.; Chang, K.; Zhang, Z.; Yuan, J.; Li, T.; Tang, W.; Zhou, E.; Xiao, Z.; Ding, L.; Zou, Y.; Zhan, X.; Yang, C.; Li, Z.; Brabec, C. J.; Li, Y.; Min, J. Suppressing Photo-Oxidation of Nonfullerene Acceptors and Their Blends in Organic Solar Cells by Exploring Material Design and Employing Friendly Stabilizers. *J. Mater. Chem. A.* **2019**, 7, 25088–25101.

- (47) Oh, J.; Lee, S.M.; Jung, S.; Lee, J.; Park, G.; Kang, S-H.; Cho, Jeong, M.; Lee, B.; Kim, S.; Yang, C. Antioxidant Additive with a High Dielectric Constant for High Photo-Oxidative Stabilization of Organic Solar Cells without Almost Sacrificing Initial High Efficiencies, *Sol. RRL* **2021**, 5, 2000812–2000821.
- (48) Cabelli, D.E.; Bielski, B.H.J. Kinetics and Mechanism for the Oxidation of Ascorbic Acid/Ascorbate by HO₂/O₂⁻ (Hydroperoxyl/Superoxide) Radicals. A Pulse Radiolysis and Stopped-Flow Photolysis Study, *J. Phys. Chem.* **1983** 87, 1809–1812.
- (49) Larson, R.A. Naturally Occurring Antioxidants, CRC-Press; 1st edition, Boca Raton, **1997**.
- (50) Speller, E. M.; Clarke, A. J.; Aristidou, N.; Wyatt, M. F.; Francas, L.; Fish, G.; Cha, H.; Lee, H. K. H.; Luke, J.; Wadsworth, A.; Evans, A. D.; McCulloch, I.; Kim, J.-S.; Haque, S. A.; Durrant, J. R.; Dimitrov, S. D.; Tsoi, W. C.; Li, Z. Toward Improved Environmental Stability of Polymer:Fullerene and Polymer:Nonfullerene Organic Solar Cells: A Common Energetic Origin of Light- and Oxygen-Induced Degradation. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, 4, 846–852.
- (51) Bendich, A.; Machlin, L.J.; Scandurra, O.; Burton, G.W.; Wayner, D. D. M. The Antioxidant Role of Vitamin C, *Advances in Free Radical Biology & Medicine* **1986**, 2, 419–444.
- (52) Trost, S.; Zilberberg, K.; Behrendt, A.; Polywka, A.; Görrn, P.; Reckers, P.; Maibach, J.; Mayer, T.; Riedl, T. Overcoming the “LightSoaking” Issue in Inverted Organic Solar Cells by the Use of Al:ZnO Electron Extraction Layers. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2013**, 3, 1437–1444.
- (53) Yang, D.; Löhrer, F. C.; Körstgens, V.; Schreiber, A.; Bernstorff, S.; Buriak, J. M.; Müller-Buschbaum, P. In-Operando Study of the Effects of Solvent Additives on the Stability of Organic Solar Cells Based on PTB7-Th:PC71BM. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, 4, 464–470.

- (54) Prosa, M.; Tessarolo, M.; Bolognesi, M.; Margeat, O.; Gedefaw, D.; Gaceur, M.; Videlot-Ackermann, C.; Andersson, M. R.; Muccini, M.; Seri, M.; Ackermann, J. Enhanced Ultraviolet Stability of Air Processed Polymer Solar Cells by Al Doping of the ZnO Interlayer. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. **2016**, 8, 1635–1643.
- (55) Ong, C.B.; Ng, L.Y.; Mohammad, A. W. A Review of ZnO Nanoparticles as Solar Photocatalysts: Synthesis, Mechanisms and Applications, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **2018**, 81, 536–551.
- (56) Dettinger, U.; Egelhaaf, H-J.; Brabec, C.J.; Latteyer, F.; Peisert, H.; Chasse, T. FTIR Study of the Impact of PC[60]BM on the Photodegradation of the Low Band Gap Polymer PCPDTBT under O₂ Environment, *Chem. Mater.* **2015**, 27, 2299–2308.
- (57) Domínguez, I.F.; Topham, P.D.; Bussiere, P-O.; Begue´. D.; Rivaton, A. Unravelling the Photodegradation Mechanisms of a Low Bandgap Polymer by Combining Experimental and Modeling Approaches, *J. Phys. Chem. C*. **2015**, 119, 2166–2176.
- (58) Razzell-Hollis, J.; Wade, J.; Chung-Tsoi, W.; Soon, Y.; Durrant, J.; Kim, J-S. Photochemical Stability of High Efficiency PTB7:PC70BM Solar Cell Blends, *J. Mater. Chem. A*. **2014**, 2, 20189–20195.
- (59) Tournebize, A.; Seck, M.; Vincze, A.; Distler, A.; Egelhaaf, H-J.; Brabec, C.J.; Rivaton, A.; Peisert, H.; Chassé, T. Photodegradation of Si-PCPDTBT:PCBM Active Layer for Organic Solar Cells Applications: A Surface and Bulk Investigation, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*. **2016**, 155, 323–330.

- (60) Tournebize, A.; Bussiere P.O.; Wong-Wah-Chung P.; Therias S.; Rivaton A.; Gardette J.L.; Beaupre S.; Leclerc M, Impact of UV-Visible Light on the Morphological and Photochemical Behavior of a Low-Bandgap Poly(2,7-Carbazole) Derivative for Use in High-Performance Solar Cells, *Advanced Energy Materials*. **2013**, 3, 478–487.
- (61) Romero, D.G.; Mario, L.D.; Portale, G.; Loi, M. A. Crystallization Driven Boost in Fill Factor and Stability in Additive-Free Organic Solar Cells, *J. Mater. Chem. A*. **2021**, 9, 23783–23792.
- (62) Pang, H-S.; Xu, H.; Tang, C.; Meng, L-K.; Ding, Y.; Xiao, J.; Liu, R-L.; Pang, Z-Q.; Huang, W. Capacitance Methodology for Investigating Defect States in Energy Gap of Organic Semiconductor, *Organic Electronics* **2019**, 65, 275–299.
- (63) Heath, J. T.; Cohen, J. D.; Shafarman, W. N. Bulk and Metastable Defects in $\text{CuIn}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x\text{Se}_2$ Thin Films Using Drive-Level Capacitance Profiling, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2004**, 95, 1000–1010.
- (64) Carr, J.A.; Chaudhary, S. On Accurate Capacitance Characterization of Organic Photovoltaic Cells, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2012**, 100, 213902–213905.
- (65) Xu, L.; Wang, J.; Hsu, J. W. P. Transport Effects on Capacitance-Frequency Analysis for Defect Characterization in Organic Photovoltaic Devices, *PHYSICAL REVIEW APPLIED* **2016**, 6, 064020–064029.
- (66) Gasparini, N.; Salvador, M.; Fladischer, S.; Katsouras, A.; Avgeropoulos, A.; Spiecker, E.; Chochos, C. L.; Brabec, C. J.; Ameri, T. An Alternative Strategy to Adjust the Recombination Mechanism of Organic Photovoltaics by Implementing Ternary Compounds. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2015**, 5, 1501527–15015233.

Table of Contents.

